
TRANSYLVANIAN REVIEW

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Mirror Histories **The Romanians as Seen** **by Themselves or by Others** **Throughout the Centuries**

Edited by
DANIELA MĂRZA • LIANA LĂPĂDATU

ROMANIAN ACADEMY
Center for Transylvanian Studies

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EDITORS' NOTE

THE ISSUE of identity, as a product of the collective imagination or as an ideological construct, has enjoyed considerable interest in the Romanian historiography of the past two decades. However, the books and articles written on this topic have by no means managed to exhaustively approach the issue. The recent developments in historical research have provided new methods and made possible the investigation of new facets of this subject.

The present volume brings to the attention of the interested readership a number of studies that come to illustrate this very reality. The aspects dealt with by the authors cover a considerable span of time and a wide range of topics. Although usually seen as a characteristic feature of the modern era, the issue of identity-building was also present in other historical periods, as demonstrated by a study devoted to the effects upon the self-image of the ethnic communities in Central and Eastern Europe of the great Mongol invasion of 1241 and of the renewed Islamic threat on the southeastern border of Christendom.

Ample space has been devoted to the modern era, in articles dealing with the relation between social status and nationhood with the Transylvanian Romanians of that time; also discussed is the manner in which, during the second half of the 19th century, the Romanian intellectuals in Transylvania endeavored to highlight some of the distinctive and specific elements of the province, presenting its culture, history and religion as features that shape its singular character. A preferred method of identity-building involved the portrayal of Transylvanian Romanians focusing on a number of mental and physical features deemed to be specific to this group. Other pieces approach the issue of the Romanians living in Bukovina, under Habsburg rule, in a multiethnic and multi-denominational space. In the same context, attention is also paid to the role of Orthodoxy

The Management of the EU's Eastern Partnership Project

A New Stage in the European Neighbourhood Policy

SIMION COSTEA

ONE OF the major geostrategic priorities of EU is to create “a ring of friends” outside its borders, a ring of friends which is to respect the European values, and also organizing a cooperation, security, stability and prosperity area. This is the reason for launching the European Neighbourhood Policy in 2003–2004, policy which refers to EU land and sea borders in the south (the Mediterranean Sea region) and in the east (the ex-Soviet region of the Black Sea).¹ The relation between EU and its neighbours stepped into a new stage in 2008, by initializing the Union for the Mediterranean and the Eastern Partnership.

Being a new project, the Eastern Partnership is a too little approached topic in the historiography or in the European studies, many aspects still being unsolved or controversial. This article aims at bringing a scientific contribution to the study of the new Eastern Partnership project, by making a critical analysis of the EU official documents and of the interested states. At the same time we will turn to good account its author's expertise and experience as a parliamentary advisor in the European Parliament (working especially in the environment of Committee on Foreign Affairs in Brussels).

The Eastern Partnership is a strategic project of EU for the consolidation of the European Neighbourhood Policy (ENP) towards the six ex-Soviet countries in Eastern Europe: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine. Therefore, all the 27 countries, members of EU and the six countries mentioned above are part of the Eastern Partnership.

At first, the project was proposed by Poland and Sweden, through their Foreign Ministers, Radoslaw Sikorski and Carl Bildt, in the General Affairs and External Relations Council on 26 May 2008, in Brussels. The project was approved by the European Council on 19–20 June 2008, together with the Union for the

Announcement on 3 December 2008, the European Council Conclusions in March 2009 and the Eastern Partnership Summit in Prague on 7 May 2009 are representative steps in defining and applying the project.²

The Summit in Prague on 7 May 2009 appointed the representatives of 33 countries (27 EU Member States and the 6 eastern republics), together with representatives of EU institutions. They adopted the Joint Declaration of the Eastern Partnership Summit, the most important document of the entire project.³

The Reason for Launching the Project and its Aims

EUROPEAN VALUES and strong geostrategic reasons are the basis of the decision to launch the new Eastern Partnership. We consider that EU has a strong geostrategic interest in having “a ring of friends” in the Black Sea area, in order to ensure its peace, security and stability at the eastern borders but also to ensure the security of its energy supply. The aim of the Eastern Partnership is developing the relations between EU and the six countries of “strategic importance,” on the basis of the European values: “democracy, the *rule of law*, respect for *human rights*, the principles of *market economy*, *sustainable development* and *good governance*.”⁴ We think that the geopolitical interests of EU are emphasised by the fact that it invited Belarus in the Eastern Partnership, a country which is not part of the ENP, a country with an authoritative pro-Moscow regime, which does not respect European values. EU wants to lure this state, which is tightly bound to Kremlin, in its “ring of friends.” Nowadays, the European Commission considers Belarus an important neighbour, interested in developing its relation with EU. Depending on its own decisions, Belarus will be able to benefit from the European Partnership and to intensify its bilateral relation with EU. Belarus has now the chance to become an active partner of EU within the ENP, on condition that the country should commit to adopting economic and democratic reforms and to advancing towards European values.⁵

From the EU point of view, ever since 1989, radical changes have occurred at its eastern borders. The successive extensions of EU in 2004 and 2007 have contributed to an even greater geographical approach of EU to its eastern neighbours. At the same time, the reforms, supported by the ENP, have allowed these countries to approach EU politically and economically. EU has an increasing responsibility to these partners, that is to help them overtake the economic and political challenges they are confronting and to answer their goals to establish stronger bonds, especially in the light of the conflict in Georgia in August 2008. After the conflict in Caucasus, the European Council on 1 September 2008 asked the Commission to present its proposition earlier than planned. “It is the right

time to open a new chapter in the relations with our eastern neighbouring countries,” said Benita Ferrero-Waldner, the European commissioner for External Relations and for the ENP.⁶

At the same time, as José Manuel Barroso (president of the Commission) said, “the aims of political association and economic integration of the European Partnership cannot be achieved unless *both sides show firm will and commitment*. We must invest more in the reciprocal stability and prosperity. These efforts will rapidly be compensated for through important economic and political benefits and they will lead to a greater stability and security both for EU and for our eastern partners.”⁷

It is true that *between the six republics there are considerable differences* concerning the political will to approach EU and the progress on the way to democracy and socio-economic development. EU does not make identical offers to all partner countries, but it takes all the differences into account. The principle of the ENP will be applied further on: how far EU will go with every country depends on the progress in the efforts to develop and reform. The Eastern Partnership is obviously related to both of the aspects: shared interests and values.⁸ Relying on the progress within the ENP, the Eastern Partnership offers bilateral and multilateral measures for an increasing cooperation. The partner countries will approach EU according to their individual ability and to the established deadlines, and EU will work with its eastern partners, on the issues related to EU, sharing experience and good practice.⁹

According to the current level of the ENP, the Eastern Partnership brings about a set of new elements:

1. New association agreements, which may include free trade agreements for the countries that are willing and ready to make such a commitment with EU;
2. Programmes, financed by EU, for improving the administrative capacity of the six republics;
3. Programmes, financed by EU, that support the economic and social development in the eastern partner countries, especially by approaching the obvious economic and social inequities in these countries;

Encouraging the development of a new free trade area, which could turn, in the long run, into a neighbouring economic community;¹⁰

Progressive integration in EU economy (by adopting a differentiated approach according to the peculiarities of the partner economies), including the making of commitments from the judicial point of view, concerning legislative approach;

6. Increased energy security for EU and its eastern partners; financing is foreseen for the investment in infrastructure, better regulations, energy efficiency and more effective systems of preventive notification in order to reduce the risk of interrupting gas supply. The Joint Declaration of the Summit in Prague

stipulates that the Eastern Partnership has the aim to consolidate the energy security through cooperation concerning energy supply and transit, stable and secure in the long run, including through better regulations, energy efficiency and by increasing the use of renewable sources of energy. Dispositions concerning the energy interdependence will be included in the new association agreements and in other bilateral agreements between EU and the partner countries. The energy cooperation will take into account the second strategic revision of the energy policy and the energy policy of each partner country;¹¹

7. Signing "mobility and security pacts," which are to ease travelling in EU for many citizens in the six republics, at the same time intensifying the efforts for corruption control, as well as for organized crime and clandestine migration control. The Commission will analyse the workers' possibilities of mobility in order to open up the labour market of EU. In the long run, gradually, through attentive evaluation, by taking particularities into account, a future "visa liberalisation" is foreseen for the citizens of the six republics who will want to travel in EU. The beneficiaries would be 76 million people who live in the six republics, 46 million being from Ukraine.¹²

8. Creating four multilateral policy platforms of cooperation (including reunions) concerning: a) democracy, good governance and stability; b) economic integration and convergence with EU policies; c) energy security; d) contacts between people with a view to supporting the reform efforts of each eastern state;¹³

9. The five flagship initiatives: a) border management programme; b) an SME facility; c) electricity markets integration, energy efficiency and renewables; d) developing the southern energy corridor; and e) cooperation concerning prevention, training and response to disasters;

10. Increased people-to-people contacts and greater involvement of civil society and other stakeholders, including the European Parliament; this is done through civil society forums and by founding the EURONEST Parliamentary Assembly;

Additional financial support for the eastern states of 350 million Euros for the period till 2013.¹⁴

Financing the Project

EU IS already financing the countries in the Eastern Partnership through bilateral programmes within the European Neighbourhood Policy. For the period between 2007 and 2010, the allocated funds are the following: Ukraine, 494 million Euros, Republic of Moldova, 209.7 million Euros, Armenia, 98.4 million Euros, Azerbaijan, 92 million Euros, Georgia, 100 million Euros

million Euros (and additional funding up to 500 million Euros available to cope with the consequences of the conflict in Georgia in August 2008).

Besides, the ENP countries can benefit from the funds from:

1. The Governance Facility (maximum 50 million Euros annually for all ENP countries);

2. The Cross Border Cooperation that brings together regions of EU Member States and ENP partner countries sharing a common land or sea border. In 2008, the CBC East adds up to approximately 25.6 million Euros;

3. The Neighbourhood Investment Facility (NIF) that operates with pooled grant resources of the Community and Member States, which are used to leverage International Financial Institutions loan financing. NIF focuses on the priority sectors Energy, Environment and Transport, but support may also be provided for SMEs and Social Sector development. There are projects ongoing ranging from Energy Transmission System, Technical assistance for Improvement of Water and Sanitation Systems, to the Modernisation Project at Chişinău Airport. In 2008 the NIF has allocated almost €70 million to projects in the East.¹⁵

What new funds does the Eastern Partnership bring? According to a document (Memo) of the European Commission, "Total assistance for the six Eastern neighbours will gradually grow from € 450 million in 2008 to € 785 million in 2013, an increase of nearly 75%. This will mean allocating a supplementary envelope of € 350 million in addition to the planned resources for the period 2010-2013. Moreover we will refocus €250 million that was already allocated to the ENP regional east programme to initiatives relevant for the implementation of the Eastern Partnership, bringing the total for implementing this new initiative to €600 million."¹⁶

The Political and Institutional Structures of the Eastern Partnership

- IN PRINCIPLE there will be biannual meetings of Heads of States or Governments involving the 27 EU Member States and the 6 partner countries of the Eastern Partnership;
- Annual meetings of Ministers of Foreign Affairs would review progress and provide more detailed political guidance;¹⁷
- Senior officials engaged in reform work in the relevant policy areas would meet at least twice a year. These meetings, prepared and chaired by the Commission, would take place within the framework of four thematic platforms (Democracy, good governance and stability; Economic integration and convergence with EU

policies, Energy security; and Contacts between people). First platform meetings in all four areas will already take place in June 2009;

- Panels to support the work of each of the platforms would meet as often as appropriate and in the format according to need;
- The EURONEST Parliamentary Assembly will be founded;
- Bilateral cooperation will continue within the structures of ENP, too.¹⁸

The Eastern Partnership aims at developing and involving the organisations of the civil society in the partner countries.¹⁹ EU Institutions think that “The development and involvement of the civil society is a key factor for the success of the democratic and market-oriented reforms. The Commission proposes to support *civil society actors and to engage them* in the initiative through the establishment of an Eastern Partnership Civil Society Forum on which consultations have already been held. The forum will promote contacts between civil society actors as well as facilitate their dialogue with public authorities.”²⁰

Defining the Eastern Partnership by comparing it to other European regional cooperation projects

ACCORDING TO the Joint Declaration of the Summit in Prague, the Eastern Partnership has a bilateral dimension (the association agreements) and a multilateral one (Summits, Ministers reunions, EURONEST). The bilateral dimension within the ENP deepens, and the multilateral dimension is an innovation. Taking part in the Eastern Partnership does not stipulate the perspective of these republics’ accession to EU, but it will respect the individual aspirations of any participant countries concerning their relations to EU.²¹ Due to its new elements mentioned above, the Eastern Partnership can be compared to the Stabilisation and Association Process, applied by EU in the western Balkans, as well as to the free trade area, previously achieved by BAFTA and CEFTA organisations. But there is also a fundamental difference: the Eastern Partnership does not offer a clear perspective of accession to EU, even though it does not reject it explicitly either. The Stabilisation and Association Process offers the statute of candidates or “potential candidates” to the involved Balkan states, so the perspective of their accession is clear, due to the will expressed by EU. There are also voices which appreciate that the Eastern Partnership does not reject the perspective of accession clearly, which could be taken into account after 2020, as Elmar Broek, MEP, ex-AFET president, said.²²

Poland, the Czech Republic and other states in central Europe have strongly supported the Eastern Partnership, from which they expect to help the ex-

Soviet countries (especially Ukraine) to become “candidate” countries. On the contrary, Germany and France do not want a membership perspective for these countries. Romania and Bulgaria have had their reserves, being afraid that the new project would undermine the current cooperation in the Black Sea region (the Black Sea Forum for Partnership and Dialogue and the Organisation of the Black Sea Economic Cooperation).²³ The European Commission appreciates that the Eastern Partnership does not harm the Black Sea Synergy (which includes the five ENP countries, plus Russia, Turkey, but not Belarus, too) and other regional cooperation initiatives.²⁴ The Black Sea Synergy aims at solving the problems which need efforts at regional level, its centre of gravity being the Black Sea. The Eastern Partnership will aim at aligning the partner countries to EU objectives and standards, and its centre of gravity will be Brussels. The European Council in March 2009 emphasised EU’s commitment to consolidate the Black Sea Synergy and to support its implementation. New partnerships within the area will be launched in the following months and years (environment, transport, but also the Black Sea Civil Society Forum).²⁵

The Eastern Partnership completes the other European initiatives of regional cooperation within EU neighbourhood: Black Sea Synergy, Northern Dimension and the Union for the Mediterranean. Unlike the Union for the Mediterranean, the Eastern Partnership has neither presidency nor its own secretary’s office, but it is administered directly by the European Commission in Brussels.

The Eastern Partnership also includes international security objectives.²⁶ Like the European Neighbourhood Policy, the Eastern Partnership wants to contribute to ensuring regional security and stability in the eastern neighbourhood of EU. The new project will encourage cooperation between the six republics lying in the European ex-Soviet space and in the extended Black Sea area. The Eastern Partnership will also try to promote trust within the region by intensifying political contacts between the partners (including between the local administrations, between politicians, between NGOs and even between the citizens of the six states). Cooperation will also be facilitated by the decrease of the trade barriers between the states. The Eastern Partnership foresees an increasing cooperation in specific fields within the Common Foreign and Security Policy including coordinating diplomatic activities and partner countries’ participation in EU missions. Preventive warning systems in security will be improved, especially in the areas affected by conflicts. They also have in view a stronger cooperation in the field of arms export and non-proliferation.²⁷

The Eastern Partnership does not include Russia, but it develops together with the Strategic Partnership EU–Russia.²⁸ Despite the accusations brought to the leaders in Kremlin, the Eastern Partnership is not an anti-Russian initiative. Through this project, EU answers to a will expressed by the countries in the

eastern neighbourhood, which want to deepen and extend their relations with EU. EU representatives always point out that the members of the Eastern Partnership will need good relations with all their neighbours, including the Russian Federation. Russia is still a strategic partner for EU, with whom they are negotiating a new comprehensive agreement.²⁹ According to the Declaration in Prague, the third states (especially Russia and Turkey!) will be eligible for participating in concrete projects, activities and reunions of track platforms, in case this participation corresponds to the objectives of the specific activities and to the general objectives of the Eastern Partnership.³⁰

The Eastern Partnership and the Difficulties of the Six Republics

UKRAINE IS very important for the Eastern Partnership, because of its enormous size, in comparison to the other five republics, its aspirations to adhere to EU after the “Orange Revolution” and its special geopolitical interest in Russia’s Foreign Policy.³¹ Poland has a very tight relation with Ukraine, for historical and geostrategic reasons. Poland has initiated the Eastern Partnership in order to meet the needs of Ukraine, and Sikorski repeatedly said that his project is meant to help the eastern countries future accession to EU. He urged the six eastern countries to follow the example of the Visegrad Group within the process of accession. Being aware of the fact that EU countries are not ready to welcome new members because of the „enlargement fatigue,” Sikorski appreciates that the eastern countries must not waste time, but should prepare for accession, in order to enter after enlargement fatigue has passed.³² Within the Eastern Partnership, Ukraine has signed a new agreement with Poland, through which the visas are replaced by simplified permits for the Ukrainian citizens who live in the border area (up to 30 km from the Polish border). More than 1.5 million people benefit from this stipulation, the agreement being in force since 1 July 2009.

At the same time, Kiev has criticised the Eastern Partnership because it brings about too few decisive progress, it does not offer a clear European perspective for Ukraine, and it does not answer to President Viktor Yushchenko and Prime Minister Yulia Tymoshenko’s strategic objective of accession to EU. Ukraine had already started negotiations with EU for new political and economic agreements (Association and Free-Trade Agreements) and had made progress in liberalising the visa regime.³³

In 2009, Ukraine worries EU, because of the instability caused by the political crisis and the competition between President Viktor Yushchenko and Prime Minister Yulia Tymoshenko (leaders of the “Orange Revolution” and support

ers of accession to EU and NATO), as well as by the tensions they have with Moscow, also fuelled by Kiev’s candidature to NATO, by the gas crisis in January 2009 etc. The opposition led by Viktor Yanukovich is very strong and has a clear pro-Russian orientation, hostile to the idea of accession to EU and NATO.

Just like Ukraine, after the “Roses Revolution” in 2003, Georgia adopted a vigorous pro-western orientation and many MEPs (Members of the European Parliament) and publicists considered it a country with many possibilities of accession to EU and NATO. But, just like Ukraine, Georgia was not invited to enter to NATO during the Summit in Bucharest in April 2008, and it was very disappointed and besides it took reprisals from Russia. The image of Georgia was deteriorated when President Mikhail Saakashvili’s regime repressed the opposition manifestations in 2007 and then after the Georgian-Russian war in August 2008. EU defends the principle of the territorial integrity of Georgia and it does not accept the independence of the breakaway regions South Ossetia and Abkhazia. But many MEPs and European diplomats criticise Saakashvili for launching the war that triggered the disproportionate Russian reaction. We consider that the Great Powers do not want to bring tensions in their relations with Moscow for the interests of a small country. Another worrying element is the attempt to overthrow the regime in Georgia in May 2009 at the exact moment when NATO started a military exercise in this country. Tbilisi attributes it to Russia.³⁴

The Republic of Moldova, during the Voronin regime (with the Party of Communists leading), was clearly orienting towards Moscow and it was the poorest country in Europe. The Voronin regime abuse against human rights was obvious in the context of the fraudulent parliamentary elections on 5 April 2009 and of the violent protests that followed. Amnesty International and many MEPs, led by Baroness Emma Nicholson, rightfully accused the communist government of repressing violently the opposition manifestations and of torturing tens of Protestants. The relations deteriorated even more after President Vladimir Voronin accused Romania of being involved in these manifestations. On the other hand, Moldova’s relations with Brussels and Moscow are complicated by the Transnistrian file.³⁵ Only after the Summit in Prague, which made the Eastern Partnership official, did anticipated elections take place in Moldova and they were won by the Coalition for European Integration, which formed the Vlad Filat government, giving new hopes to the people concerning the European perspectives of the country. Prime Minister Filat participated in a hearing in front of the Committee of Foreign Affairs in October 2009, where he expressed his pro-European orientation and the will to improve relations with Romania.³⁶

Azerbaijan has important gas and petroleum reserves, of great interest to EU, especially for the success of the Nabucco Project. Its government has turned from Moscow and approached EU in the last years. But its approach is limited

by President Ilham Aliev's tough regime, who succeeded his father Heydar Aliev in 2003 and who controls the media.³⁷

On the contrary, Armenia (3 million inhabitants) has strong relations with Moscow and it never intended to approach EU too much. Just like Azerbaijan, Armenia has an authoritarian regime, which limits the freedom of speech. In March 2008, the opposition fought the police after a series of manifestations in order to expose Serj Sargsyan's electing as president, and several tens of them were sentenced to prison.³⁸

Critical Considerations Concerning the Eastern Partnership and the Summit in Prague on 7 May 2009

THE INTERNATIONAL media has rightly noticed that the six ex-Soviet republics invited in the Eastern Partnership are either potential source of dangerous conflicts for EU or they have undemocratic regimes and are led by controversial leaders.³⁹ Belarus is "the last dictatorship in Europe," and Armenia and Azerbaijan have authoritarian regimes which violate human rights. The war in 2008 between Russia and Georgia, the gas conflict between Russia and Ukraine in January 2009, the manifestations in Moldova in April 2009 tell a lot about the instability of the region.⁴⁰ A serious issue has been raised: whether Presidents Lukashenko and Voronin should participate in the Summit in Prague or not; they are communists, known for their policy which violates human rights. After the protests and repression in Chişinău, Voronin was not eager to meet the European leaders in order to give explanations.⁴¹

Eventually, the six eastern republics were represented as follows: Republic of Moldova, represented by Mr. Andrei Stratan- Deputy Prime Minister and Minister of Foreign Affairs and for European Integration; Belarus, represented by Mr. Vladimir Semashko, first deputy prime minister of the Republic of Belarus; Armenia, represented by Mr. Serzh Sargsyan, president of the Republic of Armenia; Azerbaijan, represented by Mr. Ilham Aliyev, president of the Republic of Azerbaijan; Ukraine, represented by Mr. Viktor Yushchenko, president of Ukraine; Georgia, represented by Mr. Mikhail Saakashvili, president of Georgia.⁴²

The controversy concerning the eastern countries has been doubled by the controversy concerning the level of representation and political commitment of some EU member states. Many EU leaders' lack of interest for the Summit in Prague has been a reality criticised in political circles and the international media.⁴³ While at the Summit in Paris in May 2008, which launched the Union for the Mediterranean, the EU states were represented at the highest level (presidents

or prime ministers from 25 countries being present), at the Summit in Prague in May 2009, which launched the Eastern Partnership, there were many absents; that proves a certain lack of interest and of solidarity within EU foreign affairs. Ten EU states were not represented by presidents or prime ministers. Important leaders like Sarkozy, Zapattero, Berlusconi and presidents or prime ministers of Austria, Luxembourg, Malta and Portugal were absent. Especially Austria and Italy were represented at an improperly low level for a summit. Austria sent only its ambassador (Permanent Representative of Austria to the European Union), and Italy only the minister of Welfare. Lithuania sent only its foreign minister. From Sweden, the prime minister was present, but the one who was not there was Carl Bildt, foreign minister and one of the authors of the Eastern Partnership Project. Chancellor Angela Merkel and the German diplomats were dissatisfied with this lack of solidarity. While the new member states showed solidarity within EU for the Union for the Mediterranean project, some states from old EU-15 did not answer properly when the Eastern Partnership project was launched.⁴⁴

Some of the French political analysts consider that France has sabotaged the Eastern Partnership.⁴⁵ France is interested in developing its relations with the southern neighbours, in the Union for the Mediterranean project, but Germany interfered in order to make Sarkozy's initiative senseless. Germany is interested in developing the Eastern Partnership, but France is sabotaging it. The geopolitical interests of the Great Powers are diverging, which weakens EU Common Foreign and Security Policy. Also, the funds allocated to EU southern neighbours are much superior to those allocated to the eastern neighbours. Jean Asselborn, Foreign Minister of Luxembourg⁴⁶ emphasises that EU funds for the Southern neighbours are double in comparison to the ones for the eastern neighbours. As a rule, for each 1 Euro that goes eastwards, 2 Euros will go southwards. He said that EU must not concentrate on the controversial leaders like Saakashvili, Voronin or Lukaschenko, but that the European programmes must refer to the people, to whom they should offer positive perspectives.

Some of the influential German and French publications think that the Eastern Partnership "does not pledge" the partner countries, proving that "Brussels has no strategy for the Black Sea and the Caucasus region, no clear idea concerning the future of a cooperation with Russia." The Eastern Partnership has neither presidency nor its own secretary's office (unlike the Union for the Mediterranean), it does not offer the perspective of accession (unlike the Stabilisation and Association Process) and it does not allocate but a modest amount of 600 million Euros.⁴⁷

There have been differences of opinion between the European leaders concerning the objectives and the wording of the Declaration of Prague. A Ukrainian journalist from the *Ukrainian Press* (Kyiv) stated that during the preparatory debate

on 29 April between the ambassadors of EU member states concerning the project of the final Declaration of the Summit in Prague, "two currents of opinion" stood out. The old EU member states consider that they must maintain the conclusions adopted by the European Council in March 2009 concerning the Eastern Partnership, whereas the new member states, like Poland, the Czech Republic, Slovakia and Hungary consider that "they must go on." Another problem that was discussed was the way the six states should be called. The term "European countries" is denied by the states in Western Europe, which prefer to refer to the "Eastern countries of Europe," to the partner countries in the east. The difference is relevant, because the term "European countries" (which in Brussels generally refers to the EU member states) suggests the possibility that the six ex-Soviet republics might become EU members.⁴⁸ That is why the term "European countries" was not accepted eventually.

The Profound Causes of Russia's Hostility towards the Eastern Partnership

THE LEADERS in Moscow and the Russian media insistently affirm that the Eastern Partnership and the European Neighbourhood Policy are an expression of the Europeans' interest in increasing EU's "sphere of influence" over the countries that were under the total control of Russia two decades ago, and were considered Moscow's exclusive "sphere of interests." The Europeans and the Americans' policy is becoming increasingly incisive and pragmatic. The evolution of the USA foreign policy (from George Bush senior to Obama) is a policy oriented towards weakening Russian influence within the post-Soviet space. The Europeans are taking over the Americans' experience, fully using diplomacy, launching initiatives in the field of energy and economy in the area of the former Soviet republics.⁴⁹

From Moscow's point of view, the Russian specialist Rick Rozoff calls the Eastern Partnership "The West's Final Assault on the Former Soviet Union". In his opinion, the aim of the Eastern Partnership is "to complete the destruction of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), the Eurasian Economic Community (EurAsEC) comprised of Belarus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Russia, Tajikistan and Uzbekistan, and the only post-Soviet multinational security structure, the Collective Security Treaty Organization (CSTO), as well as to abort the formalization of the Belarus-Russia Union State. Which is to say, to isolate Russia from six of the twelve CIS states, with the other five, in Central Asia (Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan). simulta-

neously targeted by a complementary EU initiative. The ultimate intent of the Eastern Partnership is to wean away all the other ex-Soviet states from economic, trade, political, security and military ties with Russia and to integrate them into broader so-called Euro-Atlantic structures from the European Union itself initially to NATO ultimately. Coming out of last year's NATO summit in Romania the increased political, security and military integration of the EU and NATO, trumpeted by French President Nicholas Sarkozy and Foreign Minister Bernard Kouchner, warmly embraced by the Bush administration and since affirmed most strongly by British Foreign Minister David Miliband at the recent Munich Security Conference, is the yet further consolidation of the longstanding EU-NATO "soft power, hard power" division of labour mutually agreed upon. "The Partnership would demonstrate the 'power of soft power' and acknowledge that the conflict in Georgia in August 2008 had influenced the decision to launch the Partnership." In conclusion, including the ex-Soviet states in EU projects (including Nabucco) means the loss of influence for Moscow and a real surrounding of Russia. "By adding Belarus, Russia will lose its only buffer against NATO in Europe and the only substantive early warning missile surveillance and air defences it has outside its own borders. By adding Armenia, Russia will effectively be driven out of the South Caucasus. With the absorption of the five Central Asian nations, Russia would lose all influence throughout the entire former Soviet space except for its own territory."⁵⁰

These theses are also supported by authors from Republic of Moldova, from a European point of view. In Denis Cenușă's opinion, Moscow is afraid of the fact that the Polish-Swedish initiative of the Eastern Partnership can be compared to a "Stabilisation and Association Agreement" adapted to Eastern Europe, which is to strengthen the relation with EU, but it can also ease the NATO way in the area.⁵¹ Indeed, the Eastern Partnership offers effective strategic instruments of "soft power," "low and high policy," which can promote a real democratisation of the region, causing indirectly the decrease of the capacity of Russia to influence the decision making and the non-democratic political processes in the ex-Soviet republics. The partnership with EU can stimulate renewing and westernising the political class in Eastern Europe. The process may also include the numerous Russian communities in these countries, which, in the long run, could influence a future democratic transformation of the Russian society itself, affecting the Putin regime.

The project launched by the pro-American Poland aims at strengthening the energy security of the six post-Soviet states, which will increase the energy safety and stability of the whole Europe. Thus, the European pragmatism is in contradiction with the geostrategic and economic interests of Russia, which could lose the monopoly over the energy sector in the ex-Soviet space especially in

the Ukrainian one. The EU stocks in the energy sphere after the gas crisis in January 2009 (the Nabucco Project), and the launching of the Eastern Partnership are risky for the dominant position of the Russian companies owned by the state (Gazprom), which serve Kremlin's geopolitical interests. As a result, Moscow could lose control over a very powerful instrument of influence over and discord of EU. At the same time, the Eastern Partnership along with the Black Sea Synergy can establish favourable circumstances for solving the secession conflicts in the region used by Russia in order to amplify its presence in Eastern Europe.⁵²

The Dialogue and the Differences between eu and Russia concerning the Eastern Partnership

RUSSIA ACCUSED the Eastern Partnership for being an attempt to expand EU's "sphere of influence" in order to get to the energy sources. On 21 March 2009, at a forum in Brussels, the Russian Foreign Minister, Sergey Lavrov declared suggestively: "We are accused of having spheres of influence. But what is the Eastern Partnership, if not an attempt to expand EU's sphere of influence, including to Belarus?" He strongly criticised EU because it threatened Belarus with isolating it at international level if it follows Russia in recognising the independence of the Georgian breakaway regions South Ossetia and Abkhazia. "Is this promoting democracy or is it blackmail?" asked Lavrov rhetorically. Sweden (co-author of the project, together with Poland) rejected Lavrov's declaration, considering it "completely unacceptable." "The Eastern Partnership is not about spheres of influence. The difference is that these countries themselves opted to join. EU's position on Georgia is not 'blackmail' but it is about upholding the principles of EU and international law, which Russia should also be respecting," Swedish Foreign Minister Carl Bildt said at the Brussels Forum.⁵³

The EU-Russia Summit in Khabarovsk on 22 May 2009 emphasised the differences between the two parties. Instead of the EU-Russia Strategic Partnership, there was a strategic difference. Russia criticised the Eastern Partnership and refused the European Energy Charter.⁵⁴ President Medvedev considers the Eastern Partnership "partnership against Russia." He declared openly that "we do not want the Eastern Partnership to turn into a partnership against Russia", being dissatisfied with the fact that "some states view this partnership as a partnership against Russia."⁵⁵

Medvedev's declaration is in contradiction with EU leaders' favourable and conciliatory position. In order to scatter Moscow's fears, Javier Solana, EU foreign policy high representative, invited Russia to take part in some of the Eastern

Partnership programmes. The invitation was also enforced by José Manuel Barroso, president of the European Commission.

Romania's Position towards the Eastern Partnership

THE EASTERN Partnership means a stronger presence of EU in an economic and political-diplomatic interest area, declared and assumed in the long run by Romania. Under these circumstances, the initiative of the European Commission, promoted at the insistence of the Polish-Swedish diplomatic couple, coincides with Romania's objectives of cooperation within the Black Sea area, where the post-Soviet states should be included in the economic and security system of EU and NATO. Nevertheless, the Romanian diplomacy at first adopted a reserved position towards the Eastern Partnership. This attitude was determined by at least three factors: 1) the project was proposed without consulting Romania, 2) it can undermine cooperation in the Black Sea area and 3) it does not offer a clear perspective of Republic of Moldova's accession.⁵⁶

First of all, the Romanian government was not consulted. Neither was the Czech Republic nor Bulgaria. Why? Warsaw tried to avoid the possible perception according to which the Eastern Partnership is promoted by the "frustrated easterners" and preferred to cooperate with an influential state in EU, Sweden, which lies in the north of the eastern space and which was to hold presidency of EU in 2009, in the second semester. Introducing Sweden from the very beginning meant neutralising the possible opposition inside EU on behalf of the states that are more sensible to the interests of Russia in the area.⁵⁷ The Czech Republic, which took over EU Council Presidency in January 2009, joined the Polish-Swedish initiative quickly, cooperating tightly in order to give the project continuity in the second semester of 2009, the period of the Swedish Presidency. The project followed its course and Romania was to join it at the Summit in Prague on 7 May 2009.

Romania expressed its legitimate worry that the Eastern Partnership may marginalise the Black Sea Synergy (in which both Romanian diplomats and Romanian MEPs have invested a great deal), because of the geographical overlap of the two EU initiatives. But the European Commission declared that the two initiatives do not exclude each other, but they are complementary. The Black Sea Synergy has an advantage because it includes Russia and Turkey, unlike the Eastern Partnership. It can develop further on, being an answer to the EU interest of cooperation with Russia within the common neighbourhood. It can also contribute to intensifying the EU-Turkey cooperation, which can increase the chances of

accomplishing the Nabucco Project. It remains to be seen to what extent these possibilities can be accomplished. On the other hand, we consider that Romania must support the Eastern Partnership, to which it must contribute with its own objectives and means, in order to get at least part of the outcome the Black Sea Synergy already aims at.

Romania has made efforts to get a clear perspective of EU membership for the Republic of Moldova, similar to the one offered to the Western Balkans.⁵⁸ Romania succeeded in getting the declared support of the French President N. Sarkozy and good will in some of the circles in the European Commission, where Moldova is the first one to be taken into account for accession within the group of the six ex-Soviet republics, in a predictable perspective (of 10–15 years). But as it does not have enough foreign support on behalf of the EU states, and the Voronin regime has not undertaken the necessary reforms, Moldova has no real chance but to join the Eastern Partnership and to benefit from its instruments. If the new pro-European government in Chişinău (led by Prime Minister Vlad Filat) undertakes the necessary reforms, Moldova will be able to benefit from a progress within the Eastern Partnership, increasing its EU accession perspective. Romania must support Moldova to speed up the pace of the reforms in order to meet the Copenhagen criteria, necessary for accession to EU.

Romania supported the Eastern Partnership openly at the Summit in Prague, where the prime minister was present,⁵⁹ pleading for Moldova, for the cooperation at the Black Sea and for a proper relation with Russia. At the Economic Forum Romania–Russia, on 26 May 2009, in Bucharest, the Romanian president declared that “The big problems in the cooperation with Russia are the common neighbourhood at the Black Sea, recognising the independence of Abkhazia and South Ossetia, the overlap of the energy projects and Russia’s reticence towards the Eastern Partnership.”⁶⁰ In his opinion, EU must accept Russia the way it is, “include it in the common projects”, convince it to cooperate in the economic field, in a mutual advantage. In his turn, the Romanian foreign minister reaffirmed the interest of the country in the cooperation for development in the extended Black Sea area. At the same time, the dialogue about “a concrete and productive partnership” (the Eastern Partnership) should not be interpreted “as an attempt to divide this area into new spheres of influence.” In his opinion, “we can discover together more merits of the cooperation instead of competition for the influence.”⁶¹ He declared he supported the Eastern Partnership on 4 September 2009, at the Stockholm International Peace Research Institute, where the Romanian foreign minister together with the Polish Foreign Minister Radosław Sikorski participated in the Round Table with the topic “A step forward through the Eastern Partnership: challenges and opportunities.” The head of the Romanian diplomacy declared: “Twenty years ago, Romania, Poland

and other east-European nations benefited from the support, attention and assistance of the Western Community. Now, it is our turn to take a step forward, to continue the process and to give all our support to our eastern partners.” He appreciated “the visionary contribution of Sweden and Poland in the launching of the Eastern Partnership” and underlined the determination of Romania to take part in its implementation actively.⁶²

We consider that the Polish-Romanian Strategic Partnership, launched officially in Bucharest on 6 October 2009, gives new possibilities of cooperation for the success of the Eastern Partnership, for the support of a coherent European policy in the field of energy security, for making the transatlantic cooperation more effective concerning the eastern space and even for supporting more strongly the perspective of accession to EU and NATO for Ukraine and the Republic of Moldova.⁶³ As a border country of the EU, Romania should promote a proactive and effective policy for the success of this project.

IN CONCLUSION, the Eastern Partnership gives important cooperation perspectives between EU and the six republics. Achieving and developing these perspectives will depend on the progress of the six republics and on EU’s political will to support them. The EU and all 27 Member States should speak with a single voice in the EU Foreign Affairs. An effective European External Action Service (EEAS) is critical to allowing the High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy, together with the Member States and the Commission, to accomplish the strategic objectives of the EU. □

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Abstract

The Management of the eu's Eastern Partnership Project A New Stage in the European Neighbourhood Policy

This article proposes an analysis of and new approaches to the new Eastern Partnership project, which is a new stage in strengthening the European Neighbourhood Policy. The article proposes a scientific contribution to the knowledge of this important public policy of EU. By using its author's expertise in the European Parliament, the article approaches issues such as: the geostrategic reasons for launching the Eastern Partnership project and its aims, financing the project, the political and institutional structures of the Eastern Partnership: intergovernmental and parliamentary level, technical and non-governmental level. The author sets forth a series of critical considerations concerning the Eastern Partnership and the Summit in Prague on 7 May 2009, at the same time emphasizing the difficulties of the 6 Eastern republics involved: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, Moldova and Ukraine. The article presents both Russia's official speech concerning the Eastern Partnership together with the EU-Russia dialogue on this issue, and the profound causes of Russia's hostility towards the Eastern Partnership. Finally, Romania's position towards the Eastern Partnership is also presented.

Keywords

Eastern Partnership, Black Sea cooperation, European Union, international relations, institutions, policy, Russia, Belarus, Ukraine, Moldova, Romania